

Pword-report

Language name: **Tauya (LID ???) (the people call their language "Foʔu-po")**
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Sources: MacDonal, Lorna (1990) *A Grammar of Tauya*. Berlin/New York: Mouton de Gruyter.
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I Language profile (data from Ethnologue.com)

of spks: 347 (in 1981)
affiliation: **TNGP**, Madang-Adelbert Range, Adelbert Range, Brahman
Contact lgs.: Tok Pisin (modern superstrate)
Status: no official status
Prospects: not endangered yet, all ages, increasing influence from outside (since the road was built...)
Struct. results: no data

II Morpheme types

1. _____ Stem

2. _____ Restricted post-posed formative

Verb stem + *-ʔanene* '1e.PL.FUT'

- (1) *mene-ʔanene-ʔa*
stay-1e.PL.FUT-IND
'We_{EXCL} will stay.'

3. _____ Unrestricted post-posed formative

Utterance + *=o* 'VOC/INTENS/IMP'

- | | | |
|--|---|---|
| (2) <i>Aresa=o</i>
A.=VOC
'Aresa!' | (3) <i>yate-a=o</i>
go-2s.FUT=IMP
'Go!' | (4) <i>mene-a=o</i>
stay-3s.AOR=INTENS
'He stayed!' |
|--|---|---|

4. _____ Semi-restricted pre-posed formative

ya- + Noun stem (inalienable) or Verb stem '1sPOSS/1sP'

(note that all POSS prefixes are identical to the free pers. pronouns)

- (5) *ya-ʔeʔete*
1sPOSS-jaw
'my jaw'
- (6) *ya-ʔefei-ti*
1sP-get-CVB
'get me and...'

→ 4 morpheme types

III Syllable

- The maximum syllable shape is CVV. There is one single lexical (borrowed!) word with a coda: *mom* ~ *momo* 'stool, bench'. The plural forms of pers. pronouns *sen*, *ten*, *nen* (1p/2p/3p), which also occur as possessive/object prefix, lose the /n/, if it is in coda position (cf. phonological rule 9 below).
- Allowed homosyllabic vowel sequences (they do mostly not behave as one segment): /ai/, /ae/, /au/, /ao/, /ei/, /ou/, and rarely /oi/.
- No superheavy syllables!

- Stems can contain many syllables: *ʔosineimo* 'navel'
- There are monomoraic words, ([we] 'who', [te] 'I got (it)', [o] 'I pierced (it)').

IV Tone & Stress

No evidence for tone distinction.

Main stress falls on the last syllable of a word, secondary stress is assigned to the preceding alternate syllables. The initial syllable (even if footless) always bears additional secondary stress. (jambic bisyllabic (or bimoraic?) feet, assigned from the right edge of a word, including prefixes)

- (7) /ʔunuta/ → [ʔù.(nu.tá).] 'mat'
 (8) /ja-potiafo/ → [jà.(po.tì).(ja.fó).] '1sPOSS+hand' 'my hand'
 (9) /nen-pe/ → [.(nì.pé).] '3p-BEN' 'for them'

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

not attested

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

Utterance-final clitic =o 'VOC/IMP/INTENS':

Pre-vowel /e/-deletion (rule 1.1) does not work:

- (10) /borije/ + /o/ 'PN'+ 'VOC' → [borijeo] *[borijo] 'Boriye!'

But gliding (rule 1.2) and glide insertion (rule 1.3) do apply:

- (11) /irou/ + /o/ 'PN'+ 'VOC' → [irowo] 'Irou!'
 (12) /rumi/ + /o/ 'PN'+ 'VOC' → [rumijo] 'Rumi!'

VII Polymorphemic Stem forms

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

A Phonological Rules

1. Anti-V-cluster rules

Some vowel sequences (especially of two equal vowels, and sequences of more than 2 adjacent vowels) are disallowed:

Resolution 1: Pre-vocalic /e/-deletion (**not with non-cohering suffixes or clitics!**):

- (13) /fofe/ + /-a/ + /-ʔa/ 'come'+ '3.SG.AOR'+ 'IND' → [fofaʔa] 's/he came'
 (14) /borije/ + /o/ 'PN'+ 'VOC' → [borijeo] 'Boriye!', instead of *[borijo]

Resolution 2: Gliding (of high vowels between vowel and /a/):

- (15) /mei/ + /-a/ + /-ʔa/ 'cry'+ '3.SG.AOR'+ 'IND' → [mejaʔa] 's/he cried'
 (16) /jau/ + /-amu/ + /-ʔa/ 'see'+ '1.SG.FUT'+ 'IND' → [jawamuʔa] 'I will see (it)'

Resolution 3: Glide insertion between /i u o/ and vowel:

- (17) /ni/ + /-a/ + /-ʔa/ 'eat'+ '3.SG.AOR'+ 'IND' → [nijaʔa] 's/he ate'
 (18) /o/ + /-e/ 'say'+ 'n3.SG.AOR' → [owe] 'I/you_{sg} said'

Resolution 4: /n/-insertion between low vowels (only between prefix and stem)

∅ → /n/ / [+low]___(j)[+low] (but only with mono/bisyllabic stems, with one exception (21))

(19) /ja-/ + /aʔe/ '1s'+ 'eye' → [janaʔe] 'my eye'

(20) /na-/ + /jai/ '2s'+ 'footprint' → [nanaɪ] 'your_{SG} footprint' (/j/-deletion → rule 9.1)

exceptionally also with one 3-syll. stem which additionally has a nonlow vowel:

(21) /ja-/ + /oname/ '1s'+ 'hungry' → [janoname-] 'I'm hungry'

Resolution 5: Prevocalic /a/-deletion (only between prefix and stem)

/a/ → ∅ / ___+V (strictly only, when stem has initial VV sequence or initial /e/, otherwise there are exceptions, as for instance (25))

(22) /ja-/ + /ou/ '1s'+ 'shoot' → [jou-] 'shoot me'

(23) /ja-/ + /esei/ '1s'+ 'bone' → [jesei] 'my bone'

(24) /ja-/ + /osou/ '1s'+ 'push' → [josou-] 'push me'

but not in:

(25) /ja-/ + /otamo/ '1s'+ 'knee' → [jaotamo] 'my knee'

When the word is still ill-formed:

Resolution 6: Deletion of the last vowel of a vowel sequence (with regressive assimilation in [αhigh] for stem-final /VV/-sequences (cf. (28) and (29)).

The rule is blocked, when it would result in a barred vowel cluster, as in (30):

(26) /ita/ + /-a/ 'laugh'+ '3.SG.AOR' → [ita] 's/he laughed'

(27) /ʔumu/ + /-i/ + /-ʔa/ 'die'+ '3.PL.AOR'+ 'IND' → [ʔumuʔa] 'they died'

(28) /mai/ + /-e/ 'come up'+ 'n3.SG.AOR' → [mae] 'I/you_{SG} came up'

(29) /fitau/ + /-ene/ + /-ʔa/ 'throw'+ 'n3.PL.AOR'+ 'IND' → [fitaoneʔa] 'we/you_{PL} threw (it)'

(30) /mei/ + /-ene/ + /-ʔa/ 'cry'+ 'n3.PL.AOR' → [meineʔa] 'we/you_{PL} cried', instead of *meeneʔa

(31) /ou/ + /-e/ 'pierce'+ 'n3.SG.AOR' → [o] 'I/you_{SG} pierced (it)'

2. _____ Regressive vowel assimilation

/e/ → [+low] / ___ʔa (but not with non-cohering suffixes!)

(32) /mene/ + /-ʔanene/ + /-ʔa/ 'stay'+ '1e.PL.FUT'+ 'IND' → [menaʔaneneʔa] 'we_{EXCL} will stay'
(the second suffix is non-cohering!)

3. _____ Vowel deletion

/a/ → ∅ / aʔ___V

(33) /ita/ + /-ʔai/ + /-ʔa/ 'laugh'+ '3.PL.FUT'+ 'IND' → [itaʔiʔa] 'they will laugh'

but also:

(34) /ʔite/ + /-ʔai/ 'garden'+ 'ADESS' → [ʔitaʔi] 'to/in the garden'
(because of rule 2, which works before 3!)

4. _____ Progressive vowel assimilation

/e o/ → [a] / aʔ___ (+ is a morpheme boundary between prefix and stem!)

(but: for /o/ the rule is lexically determined, because there are words, where it does not work (cf. (37))!)

(35) /ja/ + /ʔeʔete/ '1sPOSS'+ 'jaw' → [jaʔaʔete] 'my jaw'

(36) /na/ + /ʔofami/ '2sP'+ 'follow' → [naʔafami-X] 'X follow(s) you_{SG}'

but:

(37) /na/ + /ʔosineimo/ '2sPOSS'+ 'navel' → [naʔosineimo] 'your_{SG} navel', instead of *[naʔasineimo]

5. _____ Unstressed vowel reduction

(disregarded in the IPA-transcriptions (as it is in the grammar) except in the following examples)

V[-stress] → [ə] / #σ(C)___ (only in non-initial syllables incl. prefixes)

Optionally, the schwa can be deleted between nasal and homorganic stop (which becomes voiced then) (cf. (38)).

(38) /ʔunuta/ → [ʔùn.nə.tá.] ~ [ʔùn.dá.] 'mat'

(39) /ja-potiafo/ → [j.à.pə.tì.jə.fó.] '1sPOSS+hand' 'my hand'

but not initially:

(40) /momune/ + /-pa/ 'sit'+CVB.SS' → [momunəpa] 'X sat and X ...'

6. High vowel deletion

V[+high] → ∅ / V___#C (only at the end of the first part of a compound or reduplication, and sometimes (highly lexicalized) between stem and suffix (cf. (43))
(but the rule does not apply strictly, cf. (44-45))

(41) /fitau/ + /fitau/ 'throw'+REDUP (INTENS) → [fitafitau] 'throw'

(42) /ʔou/ + /topi/ 'bite'+cut' → [ʔotopi] 'bite off'

(43) /ʔe ʔai-pa me ʔai-pa/

[#ʔe##ʔapa##me##ʔapa]

DEM do-CVB.SS DEM do-CVB.SS

'do this and that'

but not in:

(44) /ʔou/ + /pirire/ 'bite'+tear' → [ʔoupirire] 'tear off with teeth'

(45) /ʔai/ + /-pa/ 'do'+CVB.SS' → [ʔaipa] 'X did (it) and X ...'

7. /e/-rounding

Rule 7.1

/e/ → [+back,+round] / [LAB]___[LAB]

(46) /fofe/ + /-pa/ 'come'+CVB.SS' → [fofupa] 'X came and X ...' (the dissimilation to [u] is sporadic)

(47) /tefe/ + /-pope/ + /-a/ + /-ʔa/ 'put'+HAB'+3.SG.AOR'+IND' → [tefopopaʔa] 'S/he always put it.'

Rule 7.2

/e/ → [+back,+round] / ___(C)[+round] (recursively with prefixes, but not within stems (cf. (52))

(48) /nen-/ + /tu/ '3p'+give' → [nutu-] (/e/ rising → rule 8 below)

(49) /sen-/ + /suʔutu/ '1p'+ask' → [susuʔutu-] 'ask us' (dito)

(50) /sen-/ + /otamo/ '1p'+knee' → [sonotamo] 'our knees'

(51) /ten-/ + /potijafo/ '2p'+hand' → [tonopotijafo] 'your_{PL} hands' (vowel epenthesis → rule 9.3 below)

and also:

(52) /nen-/ + /ʔʷanenemo/ '3p'+shadow' → [noʔanenemo] 'their shadows' (delabialization → rule 10 below)

Rule 7.3

/e/ → [+back,+round] / ___+ʔ (only between prefix and stem)

(53) /nen-/ + /ʔate/ '3p'+hit' → [noʔate-] 'hit them' (/n/-deletion → rule 9.4)

8. /e/-rising

/e/ → [+high] / (verb stem/deictic/pron.X___#)

between compound parts (the following 5 auxiliaries are treated as such):

(54) /ese/ + /#mene/ 'hear'+STAT(lit.: stay)' → [esimene-] 'know'

(55) /te/ + /#fe/ 'get'+TR.PERF' → [tife-] 'have got (it)'

- (56) /jate/ + /#ti/ 'go'+ 'INTR.PERF' → [jatiti-] 'have gone'
 (57) /te/ + /#we/ 'get'+ 'CONATIVE' → [tiwe-] 'try to get'
 (58) /mene/ + /#ʔafe/ 'stay'+ 'PROG' → [miniʔafe-] 'be staying' (assimilation of the first /e/ is sporadic)

between compound of a verb stem and a verbalized pronoun:

- (59) /jate/ + /#fei/ + /-fe/ 'go'+ '3s'+ 'TR' → [jatifeife-] 'make her/him go'
 (60) /te/ + /#ja/ + /-fe/ 'get'+ '1s'+ 'TR' → [tjafe-] 'get (it) for me'

with some pronouns/deictics:

- (61) /ʔe/ 'DEM' → [ʔi] 'that (one)'
 (62) /ne/ '3s' → [ni] 's/he' (but with [e], when it occurs as prefix)

but not, for instance, with suffixal auxiliaries:

- (63) /te/ + /-pope/ 'get'+ 'HAB' → [tepepe-] 'always get'

The rule is also blocked, when the unproductive derivational suffix *-ne* is used at the verb stem:

- (64) /momu-ne/ + /#we/ 'sit'+ 'CONATIVE' → [momune-we-] 'try to sit/sit a little'
 (65) /ʔuti-ne/ + /#ja/ + /-fe/ 'fall'+ '1s'+ 'TR' → [ʔutinejafe-] 'drop me'

9 _____ Anti-C-cluster rules

C-clusters are disliked.

Resolution 1: /j/-deletion

/j/ → ∅ / C_____ (only possible, when personal pronouns, which have a nasal coda, appear as prefix)

- (66) /sen-/ + /jau/ '1p'+ 'see' → [senau-] 'see us'
 (67) /ten-/ + /jai/ '2p'+ 'footprint' → [tenai] 'your_{PL} footprints'

Resolution 2: Melting of N-Stop clusters

[-son, -cont] → [+voiced] / [+nas]_____ (the result is a prenasalized voiced stop, which is treated as one segment, underlying non-initial voiced stops (only occur in loans) become generally prenasalized, cf. (68-69))

(the rule can only apply, when an unstressed vowel is deleted, and **does not apply between prefix and stem or between stem and suffix!**)

- (68) /abo/ 'namesake' (loan) → [a^mbo]
 (69) /feregarija/ 'mother-of-pearl' (loan) → [fere^ŋgarija]
 (70) /ʔunuta/ 'mat' → [ʔuⁿda]

but not in:

- (71) /ten/ + /-pe/ '2p'+ 'BEN' → [tipe], instead of *[te^mbe]
 (72) /nen-/ + /tu/ '3p'+ 'give' → [nutu-], instead of *[neⁿdu-] (/e/ rising → rule 8 above, /e/-rounding → rule 7.2 above)

Resolution 3: Vowel epenthesis

∅ → [e] / C_____+{m p w} (but lexically determined)

- (73) /ten-/ + /potijafo/ '2p'+ 'hand' → [tonopotijafo] 'your_{PL} hands' (/e/-rounding → rule 7.2 above)
 (74) /sen-/ + /momo/ '1p'+ 'body' → [sononomo] 'our bodies' (dito, note sporadic nasal POA assimilation)
 (75) /sen-/ + /muʔare/ '1p'+ 'forehead' → [sunumuʔare] 'our foreheads' (dito, /e/-rising → rule 8)
 (76) /nen-/ + /wase/ '3p'+ 'watch(v)' → [nonowase-] 'watch them' (dito)
 (77) /ten/ + /-pi/ '2p'+ 'GEN' → [tinipi] 'your_{PL}' (dito, /e/-rising → rule 8)

but not in:

- (78) /sen-/ + /maʔa/ '1p'+ 'tooth' → [semaʔa] 'our teeth'

Resolution 4: Coda deletion

C → ∅ / ___)ₑ (but only if resolutions 1-3 do not apply)

- (79) /sen/ '1p' → [si] (/e/ rising can be found as rule 8 above)
(80) /ten/ + /-pe/ '2p'+ 'BEN' → [tipe] (dito)
(81) /sen-/ + /suʔutu/ '1p'+ 'ask' → [susuʔutu-] 'ask us' (dito, /e/-rounding → rule 7.2 above)
(82) /ten-/ + /pare/ '2p'+ 'neck' → [tepare] 'your_{PL} necks'
but not:
(83) /sen-/ + /otamo/ '1p'+ 'knee' → [sonotamo] 'our knees'

10 _____ Delabialization

/ʔ^w/ → [-round] / C+___

- (84) /nen-/ + /ʔ^wanenemo/ '3p'+ 'shadow' → [noʔanenemo] 'their shadows'

B Phonotactic Constraints

/k k^w/ occur only word-initially (very few exceptions for /k/, as [jauke] 'dugong'), but are retained in reduplicated forms:

- (85) /k^wa/ ~ /k^wa-ne/ 'REDUP'~'be small-DERIV' → [k^wak^wane-] 'be small'
(86) /kotu/ ~ /kotu-ne/ 'REDUP'~'crash/pound-DERIV' → [kotukotune] 'crash, pound'

Most probably, /k k^w/ remain also, when prefixes occur, but there are no examples.

IX Reduplication

see rules above, if there is a different application of them

X Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena

no data

XI Other Special things

not available